

Scurvy during Richard Hawkins' voyage (1593)

by Harri Hemilä

Richard Hawkins described symptoms consistent with scurvy during a voyage in 1593. This account represents one of the earliest historically documented descriptions of scurvy, and one of the earliest recorded uses of the word *scurvy* in the English language. Hawkins also reported that oranges and lemons were effective in treating the symptoms.

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Yellow is used to indicate the more important sections such as the symptoms of scurvy.

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This annotated version was prepared by:

Harri Hemilä, University of Helsinki, Finland

<https://www.mv.helsinki.fi/home/hemila>

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4710-307X>

<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/?term=hemila+h>

<https://scholar.google.com/citations?user=2mkomzUAAAAJ>

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The earliest recorded occurrence of scurvy on long sea voyages appears to have been during Vasco da Gama's first voyage to India (1497-1499).¹ Scurvy also afflicted the crew on Magellan's circumnavigation of the globe (1519-1522).² Thereafter, large numbers of sailors suffered from the disease throughout the Age of Sail.^{3, 4, 5, 6, 7} In the English Navy, the incidence of scurvy declined dramatically at the end of the 1700s when lime and lemon juice were made obligatory to sailors.^{8, 9}

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- 1 Scurvy during Vasco da Gama's first voyage (1497-1499).
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17781205>
<https://www.gutenberg.org/ebooks/46440>
 - 2 Scurvy during Magellan's voyage around the world (1519-1522).
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18001194>
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC1806596>
<https://www.gutenberg.org/ebooks/74723> p.64-65
 - 3 Lind J (1772) A Treatise on the Scurvy.
<https://archive.org/details/treatiseonscurvy1772lind/page/n5/mode/2up>
 - 4 Kenneth J Carpenter (1986) The History of Scurvy and Vitamin C: The explorers' sickness; p.1-28.
<https://www.cambridge.org/fi/universitypress/subjects/history/history-medicine/history-scurvy-and-vitamin-c>
 - 5 Scurvy on John Davis' voyage (1591-1593).
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17884408>
 - 6 Thomas Stephens, S. J., the First Englishman in India. Scurvy on p.238.
<https://www.jstor.org/stable/607122> p.
 - 7 Scurvy on Anson's voyage round the world (1740-1744).
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17397300>
<https://www.gutenberg.org/ebooks/16611>
<https://www.gutenberg.org/ebooks/47130>
 - 8 Budd G (1840) Scurvy.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17455962>
 - 9 Between the years 1779 and 1813, the diminution of sick and of deaths in the British navy was in the proportion of four to one. In 1779, 1:2.45 were sick, and in 1813, 1:10.75 were sick, corresponding to decline by ratio 4.4.
Table 1, p.539-540 in:
Blane G (1815) Statements of the comparative Health of the British Navy, from the year 1779 to the year 1814.
<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC2129027>

The description of scurvy on Richard Hawkins' voyage (1593) is so dramatic that the report was selected as a Nutrition Classic:

<https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/3540742>

<https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1753-4887.1986.tb07575.x>

In his treatise, James Lind (1772)¹⁰ wrote about Hawkins' voyage as follows:

It is now above 150 years since that great sea-officer, Sir Richard Hawkins, in his observations made in a voyage to the South sea, remarked it [scurvy] to be the pestilence of that element [sea]. He was able, in the course of twenty years, in which he had been employed at sea, to give an account of 10,000 mariners destroyed by it.¹¹ [p.60 in the 1847 reprint]

In his authoritative book "*The History of Scurvy and Vitamin C*", Kenneth Carpenter (1986; p.15-17)¹² summarized the symptoms of scurvy on the voyage by Richard Hawkins as follows:

Sir Richard Hawkins led another expedition in 1593. He had been a leader in the fight against the Armada, and both his father and grandfather had been famous sea captains. Twenty years after his return, he published his "observations" on the voyage... Because of contrary winds, it was not until mid-October, and with only four men still healthy, that they were able to go ashore – at Santos in southern Brazil. There, under a flag of truce the Portuguese allowed them to trade cloth for oranges and lemons. [p.78-79 in the 1847 reprint]

There was great joy amongst my company; and many, with the sight of the oranges and lemons, seemed to recover heart. This is a wonderful secret of the power and wisdom of God, that hath hidden so great and unknown virtue in this fruit, to be a certain remedy for this infirmity; I presently caused them all to be divided amongst our sick men, which were so many, that there came not above three or four to a share. [p.81-82 in the 1847 reprint]

Hawkins then considered the diseases at some length: "The signs to know this disease in the beginning are divers: by the swelling of the gums, by denting of the flesh of the legs with a mans finger, the pit remaining without filling up in a good space. Others show it with their laziness: others complain of the crick of the back, etc., all which are, for the most part, certain tokens of infection." ... He added;

That which I have seen most fruitful for this sickness, is sour oranges and lemons... [p.60]

10 <https://archive.org/details/treatiseonscurvy1772lind/page/n13/mode/2up> p.viii.

<https://wellcomecollection.org/works/r7fpbavt/items?canvas=14>

11 It seems highly unlikely that the quite often repeated Hawkins' statement of "10,000" is based on accurate calculations; rather it is better to interpret it as "lots of" or "thousands".

12 Kenneth J Carpenter (1986) *The History of Scurvy and Vitamin C*.

<https://www.cambridge.org/fi/universitypress/subjects/history/history-medicine/history-scurvy-and-vitamin-c>

However, Carpenter was not convinced that all the symptoms described by Hawkins were explained by scurvy, and he speculated that there might also have been beri-beri:

Excerpts from Sir Richard Hawkins observations... in relation to scurvy – which, from the descriptions, was probably combined with beriberi (p.16).

However, Carpenter did not give any arguments to the opinion that the symptoms reported on Hawkins' voyage would not be scurvy. Given that vitamin C is the substance particularly relevant in oranges and lemons, and that Hawkins described that the disease was cured with them, there is no need to speculate about beri-beri to explain the main symptoms.

In his book, Carpenter (1986; p.14-15) also commented on the symptoms reported on John Davis' voyage (1591-1593) that "Obviously this disease was not scurvy". Here also, Carpenter did not give any argument for the statement, instead he referred to Creighton's (1891) earlier text, in which Creighton did not give valid arguments for rejecting scurvy.¹³

Creighton noted that the sailors on Davis' voyage had dropsy and dyspnoea, but those symptoms are not inconsistent with scurvy, instead they are quite common symptoms of severe scurvy.¹⁴ Richard Hawkins reported that "my company within a few days began to fall sick of a disease which sea-men call scurvy: and seems to be a kind of dropsy."¹⁵ (see below p.56 in the 1847 reprint of Hawkins' book). Probably this mention of dropsy was interpreted by Carpenter as an indication that there might be also something else than scurvy. Apparently, in many cases of scurvy, there is shortage of many other nutrients; nevertheless, dropsy is one of the symptoms of severe scurvy.

13 Creighton wrote about the Davis' (1591-1593) voyage:
"The remarkable epidemic ... was probably not scurvy, or at least not all scurvy: the dropsy and dyspnoea suggest one of the two forms of beri-beri, of a peculiarly severe type"
A history of epidemics in Britain by Creighton, Charles (1891), p.592-593.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17882745>
<https://archive.org/details/historyofepidemi01unse/page/592/mode/2up>
<https://archive.org/details/historyofepidemi01crei/page/592/mode/2up>
<https://catalog.hathitrust.org/Record/001559476>

14 Scurvy on John Davis' voyage (1591-1593)
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17884409>

15 Dropsy. See Footnote 19.

The Observations of Sir Richard Hawkins, Knight, in his Voyage into the South Sea. AD 1593.

The 1622 version,

Scurvy on pages 35-37.

https://archive.org/details/cihm_18326/page/n40/mode/2up

https://archive.org/details/observationsofsi00hawk_0/page/34/mode/2up

<https://babel.hathitrust.org/cgi/pt?id=aeu.ark:/13960/t3qv4383j&seq=46>

https://archive.org/details/cihm_18326/page/n40/mode/2up

The 1847 reprint,

Scurvy on pages 56-61.

<https://www.gutenberg.org/ebooks/57502>

<https://archive.org/details/observationsofsi00hawkrich/page/56/mode/2up>

<https://archive.org/details/observationsofsi00hawk/page/56/mode/2up>

<https://archive.org/details/observationssir00bethgoog/page/n76/mode/2up>

<https://archive.org/details/observationssir01bethgoog/page/n78/mode/2up>

<https://archive.org/details/observationssir02bethgoog/page/n77/mode/2up>

https://archive.org/details/cihm_36497/page/n72/mode/2up

<https://archive.org/details/dli.ministry.04871/page/56/mode/2up>

<https://babel.hathitrust.org/cgi/pt?id=aeu.ark:/13960/t7gq7pg9v&seq=77>

<https://babel.hathitrust.org/cgi/pt?id=hvd.32044010183309&seq=76>

The 1878 reprint with Introduction by Clements R Markham¹⁶

Scurvy on pages 138-142.

<https://archive.org/details/hawkinsvoyagesdu00markrich/page/138/mode/2up>

<https://babel.hathitrust.org/cgi/pt?id=yale.39002005811352&seq=204>

<https://archive.org/details/hawkinsvoyagesd00figugooog/page/138/mode/2up>

<https://archive.org/details/hawkinsvoyagesd00hawkgoog/page/120/mode/2up>

Richard Hawkins

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Richard_Hawkins

<https://www.britannica.com/biography/Richard-Hawkins>

<https://www.rmg.co.uk/collections/objects/rmgc-object-15598>

<https://www.historyofparliamentonline.org/volume/1604-1629/member/hawkins-sir-richard-1560-1622>

<https://www.tudorsociety.com/sir-richard-hawkins-1560-1622>

<https://www.britishempire.co.uk/biography/richardhawkins.htm>

<https://artuk.org/discover/artworks/admiral-sir-richard-hawkins-15621622-172676>

See also Editor's Preface (1847) and Introduction (1878) at the end of this document.

¹⁶ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Clements_Markham

<https://www.rgs.org/our-collections/stories-from-our-collections/explore-our-collections/portrait-of-sir-clements-markham>

The Observations of Sir Richard Hawkins, Knight, in his Voyage into the South Sea.

Only a few footnotes of the 1847 and 1878 reprints are shown, see the digitized versions for all footnotes.

SECTION XV.

<https://archive.org/details/observationsofsi00hawk/page/52/mode/2up>

Here is to be noted, that the error which we fell into in our accompts, was such as all men fall into where are currants that set east or west, and are not knowne; for that there is no certaine rule yet practised for triall of the longitude, as there is of the latitude, though some curious and experimented of our nation, with whom I have had conference about this poynt, have shewed me two or three manner of wayes how to know it.

p.53

This, some years before, was the losse of the *Edward Cotton*, bound for the coast of Brasill, which taken with the winde contrary neere the lyne, standing to the eastwards, and making accompt to be fiftie or sixtie leagues¹⁷ off the coast, with all her sayles standing, came suddenly a ground upon the sholes of Madre-bomba, and so was cast away, though the most part of their company saved themselves upon raffles; but with the contagion of the countrie, and bad entreatie which the negros gave them, they died; so that there returned not to their country above three or foure of them.

p.54

But God Almightye dealt more mercifully with us, in shewing us our error in the day, and in time that wee might remedie it; to him be evermore glory for all.

This currant from the line equinoctiall, to twentie degrees northerly, hath great force, and setteth next of any thing east, directly upon the shore; which we found by this meanes: standing to the westwards, the wind southerly, when we lay with our ships head west, and by south, we gayned in our heith more then if wee had made our way good west south-west; for that, the currant tooke us under the bow; but lying west, or west and by north, we lost more in twelve houres then the other way we could get in foure and twentie. By which plainly we saw, that the currant did set east next of any thing. Whether this currant runneth ever one way, or doth alter, and how, we could by no meanes understand, but tract of time and observation will discover this, as it hath done of many others in sundry seas.

17 League. A historical unit of distance.

In the UK, one league was about 5 km.

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/English_units_of_measurement#Length

[https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/League_\(unit\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/League_(unit))

The currant that setteth betwixt New-found-land and Spaine, runneth also east and west, and long time deceived many, and made some to count the way longer, and others shorter, according as the passage was speedie or slowe; not knowing that the furtherance or hinderance of the currant was cause of the speeding or flowing of the way. And in sea cardes I have seene difference of above thirtie leagues betwixt the iland Tercera, and the mayne. And others have recounted unto me, that comming from the India's, and looking out for the ilands of Azores, they have had sight of Spaine. And some have looked out for Spaine, and have discovered the ilands.

p.55

The selfe same currant is in the Levant sea, but runneth trade betwixt the maynes, and changeable sometimes to the east-wards, sometimes to the west-wards.

In Brasill and the South sea, the currant likewise is changeable, but it runneth ever amongst the coast, accompanying the winde: and it is an infallible rule, that twelve or twentie foure houres before the winde alters, the currant begins to change.

In the West Indies onely the currant runneth continually one way, and setteth amongst the coast from the equinoctiall lyne towards the north. No man hath yet found that these courrants keepe any certaine time, or run so many dayes, or moneths, one way as another, as doth the course of ebbing and flowing, well knowne in all seas; only neere the shore they have small force; partly, because of the reflux which the coast causeth, and partly for the ebbing and flowing, which more or lesse is generall in most seas.

When the currant runneth north or south, it is easily discovered by augmenting or diminishing the height; but how to know the setting of the currant from east to west in the mayne sea, is difficult; and as yet I have not knowne any man, or read any authour, that hath prescribed any certaine meane or way to discover it. But experience teacheth that in the mayne sea, for the most part, it is variable; and therefore the best and safest rule to prevent the danger (which the uncertainty and ignorance heereof may cause), is carefull and continuall watch by day and night, and upon the east and west course ever to bee before the shipp, and to use the meanes possible to know the errour, by the rules which newe authours may teach; beating off and on, somtimes to the west-wards, sometimes to the east-wards, with a fayre gale of winde.

p.56

SECTION XVI.

<https://archive.org/details/observationsofsi00hawk/page/56/mode/2up>

The scurvey.¹⁸

p.56

Being betwixt three or foure degrees of the equinoctiall line, my company within a few dayes began to fall sicke, of a disease which sea-men are wont to call the scurvey; and seemeth to bee a kind of dropsie,¹⁹ and raigneth most in this climate of any that I have heard or read of in the world; though in all seas it is wont to helpe and increase the miserie of man; it possesseth all those of which it taketh hold, with a loathsome sloathfulnesse, even to eate: they would be content to change their sleepe and rest, which is the most pernicious enemie in this sicknesse, that is knowne. It bringeth with it a great desire to drinke, and causeth a generall swelling of all parts of the body, especially of the legs and gums, and many times the teeth fall out of the jawes without paine.

The signes.

The signes to know this disease in the beginning are divers: by the swelling of the gummes, by denting of the flesh of the leggs with a man's finger, the pit remayning without filling up in a good space.¹⁹ Others show it with their lasinesse: others complaine of the cricke of the backe,²⁰ etc., all which are, for the most part, certaine tokens of infection.

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- 18 This is one of the earliest use of term "scurvy" in English. According to Oxford English Dictionary: First use in 1589: "Our legs now [us deceive,] swolne euery ioint withall, With this disease, which, by your leaue, the Scuruie men doe call." Hakluyt, Principall Navigations 1589; i. 139. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17941245> https://archive.org/details/cihm_35668/page/n158/mode/2up
- 19 Dropsy. The historical diagnosis of dropsy – which is now obsolete – indicated simply an abnormal accumulation of fluid. The word derives from the Greek hydrops (water). Alternative or supplementary terms included hydrothorax (fluid in the chest cavity), ascites (which still indicates excess free fluid in the abdominal cavity), anasarca (still used to describe generalized edema throughout the body). <https://doi.org/10.1017/CHOL9780521332866.101>
Dropsy. An ancient medical term used to indicate different conditions including chronic heart failure. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijcard.2017.07.104>
Scurvy can cause heart failure, eg. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/38504249> <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/35282368> <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/38464798> <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/27682441>
- 20 Pain in the legs is a common symptom of scurvy. e.g. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17455962> <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10685194> <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/15797491>

The cause.

The cause of this sicknes some attribute to sloath; some to conceite; and divers men speake diversly: that which I have observed is, that **our nation is more subject unto it then any other;** because being bred in a temperate clymate, where the naturall heate restrayned, giveth strength to the stomacke, sustayning it with meates of good nourishment, and that in a wholesome ayre; whereas comming into the hot countries (where that naturall heate is dispersed through the whole body, which was wont to be proper to the stomache; and the meates for the most part preserved with salt, and its substance thereby diminished, and many times corrupted), greater force for digestion is now required then in times past; but the stomache finding less virtue to doe his office, in reparting to each member his due proportion in perfection, which either giveth it rawe, or remayneth with it indigested by his hardnes or cruditie, infeebleth the body, and maketh it unlustie and unfit for any thing; for the stomache being strong (though all parts els be weake), there is ever a desire to feede, and aptnes to perform whatsoever can be required of a man; but though all other members be strong and sound, if the stomache be opprest, or squemish, **all the body is unlustie, and unfit for any thing, and yeeldeth to nothing so readily as sloathfulnes,** which is confirmed by the common answeere to all questions: as, will you eate? will you sleepe? will you walke? will you play? The answeere is, I have no stomache: which is as much as to say, no, not willingly: thereby confirming, that without a sound and whole stomache, nothing can bee well accomplished, nor any sustenance well digested.²¹

Seething of meat in salt water.

The seething of the meate in salt water, helpeth to cause this infirmitie, which in long voyages can hardly be avoyded: but if it may be, it is to be shunned; for the water of the sea to man's body is very unwholesome. The corruption of the victuals, and especially of the bread, is very pernicious; the vapours and ayre of the sea also is nothing profitable, especially in these hot countries, where are many calmes. And were it not for the moving of the sea by the force of windes, tydes, and currants, it would corrupt all the world.

21 Footnote in the 1847 reprint: The cause of scurvy is now known to be, the use for a long period of one diet, and that unwholesome. Since greater attention has been paid to the proper admixture of articles of food, and also to the cleanliness and ventilation of the vessel, this disease has nearly disappeared.

The experience I saw in anno 1590, lying with a fletee of her majesties ships about the ilands of the Azores, almost six moneths; the greatest part of the time we were becalmed: with which all the sea became so replenished with several sorts of gellyes, and formes of serpents, adders, and snakes, as seemed wonderfull: some greene, some blacke, some yellow, some white, some of divers coulours; and many of them had life, and some there were a yard and halfe, and two yards long; which had I not seene, I could hardly have beleevd. And hereof are witnesses all the companies of the ships which were then present; so that hardly a man could draw a buckett of water cleere of some corruption. In which voyage, towards the end thereof, many of every ship (saving of the *Nonperail*, which was under my charge, and had onely one man sicke in all the voyage), fell sicke of this disease, and began to die apace, but that the speedie passage into our country was remedie to the crazed, and a preservative for those that were not touched. The best prevention for this disease (in my judgement) is to keepe cleane the shippe; to besprinkle her ordinarily with vinegar, or to burne tarre, and some sweet savours; to feed upon as few salt meats in the hot country as may be; and especially to shunne all kindes of salt fish, and to reserve them for the cold climates; and not to dresse any meate with salt water, nor to suffer the companie to wash their shirts nor cloathes in it, nor to sleepe in their cloaths when they are wett. For this cause it is necessarily required, that provision be made of apparell for the company, that they may have wherewith to shift themselves; being a common calamitie amongst the ordinary sort of mariners, to spend their thrift on the shore, and to bring to sea no more cloaths then they have backes. For the bodie of man is not refreshed with any thing more then with shifting cleane cloaths; a great preservative of health in hott countries.

p.59

The second antidote is, to keepe the companie occupied in some bodily exercise of worke, of agilitie, of pastimes, of dauncing, of use of armes; these helpeth much to banish this infirmitie. Thirdly, in the morning, at discharge of the watch, to give every man a bit of bread, and a draught of drinke, either beere or wine mingled with water (at the least, the one halfe), or a quantitie mingled with beere,

that the pores of the bodie may be full, when the vapours of the sea ascend up.²²

The morning draught should be ever of the best and choysest of that in the ship. Pure wine I hold to be more hurtfull then the other is profitable. In this, others will be of a contrary opinion, but I thinke partiall. If not, then leave I the remedies thereof to those physitions and surgeons who have experience; and I wish that some learned man would write of it, for it is the plague of the sea, and the spoyle of mariners. Doubtlesse, it would be a meritorious worke with God and man, and most beneficiall for our countrie; for in twentie yeares, since that I have used the sea, I dare take upon me to give accompt of ten thousand men consumed with this disease.²³

p.60

By sower oranges and lemons.

That which I have seene most fruitfull for this sicknesse, is sower oranges and lemmons,²⁴ and a water which amongst others (for my particular provision) I carryed to the sea, called Dr. Stevens his water, of which, for that his vertue was not then well knowne unto me, I carryed but little, and it tooke end quickly, but gave health to those that used it.

22 Footnote in the 1847 reprint: It forms part of a naval surgeon's instructions, that in tropical countries, when the crew are likely to be employed on shore, each is to take a morning draught of spirits or wine, with bark infused.

23 It seems highly unlikely that the quite often repeated Hawkins' statement of "10,000" is based on accurate calculations; rather it is better to interpret it as "lots of" or "thousands".

24 Footnote in the 1847 reprint: The scurvy is not peculiar to seamen. It raged with great violence during the siege of Gibraltar. Oranges and lemons were found of great benefit in arresting the disease. Lime juice has been long a fixed article of diet in men-of-war, and lately merchant vessels are compelled to carry it as an article of provision.

Note by HH: Many scurvy epidemics have been caused by sieges, e.g.:

Siege of Breda (1624)

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17225428>

Siege of Thorn (1703)

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17225782>

Siege of Alexandria (1801)

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15582455>

By oyle of vitry.²⁵

The oyle of vitry is beneficial for this disease; taking two drops of it, and mingled in a draught of water, with a little sugar. It taketh away the thirst, and helpeth to cleanse and comfort the stomache. But the principall of all, is the ayre of the land; for the sea is naturall for fishes, and the land for men. And the oftener a man can have his people to land, not hindering his voyage, the better it is, and the profitablest course that he can take to refresh them.²⁶

25 Diluted sulfuric acid.

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Sulfuric_acid

https://en.wiktionary.org/wiki/oil_of_vitriol

26 Footnote in the 1878 reprint by Clements R Markham:

These are very interesting remarks on the scurvy. Sir Richard Hawkins takes a broader and more scientific view of the question than do the bigoted “lime-juicers” of the present day. The cause of scurvy is the absence of fresh food. The preventives, as Sir Richard truly says, are fresh food, good ventilation, cleanliness, and bodily exercise with amusements. Medicines, such as lime-juice, “Dr. Stevens his water”, and “oyle of vitry”, take a secondary place. They may help both as cures and preventives, but with other circumstances tending to produce the disease, lime-juice alone will neither prevent nor cure. The “Scurvy Committee”, which recently reported on the outbreak in the Arctic Expedition of 1875-76 came to conclusions directly opposed to the evidence. None of the extended travelling parties of former Arctic expeditions took lime-juice except on one occasion, and on that one occasion alone was there an outbreak of scurvy. During the late expedition itself scurvy broke out in eight cases, when men were taking lime-juice regularly. The whole mass of evidence confirmed all former Arctic experience, and showed that the absence of lime-juice on some of the sledges was not the cause of the outbreak of scurvy. In the cases where lime-juice was not taken on sledges, the reason was that it could not have been used in the intense cold. The evidence also proved that lime-juice alone, without fresh food, will not cure the scurvy. Lime-juice, as Sir James Lancaster and Sir Richard Hawkins discovered three centuries ago, is an excellent medicine in helping to arrest the disease; but without the aid of good ventilation, cleanliness, and fresh food, lime-juice alone will neither prevent nor cure. The opposite conclusion of the “Scurvy Committee” is opposed to all the evidence they took, and to all experience. Of course every precaution should be taken against scurvy, and, as soon as fresh vegetable food is absent, daily rations of lime-juice must be taken when it is possible. In sledge travelling in the Arctic Regions, during April and May, it is not possible to take lime-juice in the form in which it is supplied to ships; and Sir George Nares was quite right not to send it.

For some further notices of outbreaks of scurvy in these early voyages, see the *Voyages of Sir James Lancaster*, etc., a volume issued by the Hakluyt Society in 1878, pages 4, 61, 62, 113, 222.

<https://archive.org/details/hawkinsvoyagesdu00markrich/page/142/mode/2up>

Note by HH: Markham’s comments on lime juice were false, see eg. Carpenter (1986) and Chick H. Early investigations of scurvy and the antiscorbutic vitamin.

<https://doi.org/10.1079/PNS19530050>

SECTION XVII.

The company sicke and dismayed.

p.61

Having stood to the westwards some hundreth leagues and more, and the wind continuing with us contrarie, and the sicknesse so fervent, that every day there dyed more or lesse,—my companie in generall began to dismay, and to desire to returne homewards, which I laboured to hinder by good reasons and perswasions; as that to the West Indies we had not above eight hundreth leagues, to the ilands of Azores little lesse, and before we came to the ilands of Cape de Verde, that we should meete with the breze; for every night we might see the reach goe contrary to the winde which wee sayled by; verifying the old proverbe amongst mariners,—that he hath need of a long mast, that will sayle by the reach: and that the neerest land and speediest refreshing we could look for, was the coast of Brasill; and that standing towards it with the wind we had, we shortned our way for the Indies; and that to put all the sicke men together in one shippe, and to send her home, was to make her their grave. For we could spare but few sound men, who were also subject to fall sicke, and the misery, notwithstanding, remedillesse. With which they were convinced, and remayned satisfied. So leaving all to their choyse, with the consideration of what I perswaded, they resolved, with me, to continue our course, till that God was pleased to looke upon us with his Fatherly eyes of mercie.

...

SECTION XXI.

<https://archive.org/details/observationsofsi00hawk/page/76/mode/2up>

Betwixt nineteene and twenty degrees to the south-wards of the lyne, the winde tooke us contrary, which together with the sicknes of my people made mee to seeke the shore; and about the end of October, we had sight of the land, which presently by our height and the making of it, discovered it selfe to be the port of Santos, alias Nostra Señora de Victoria, and is easie to be knowne, for it hath a great high hill over the port, which (howsoever a man commeth with the land) riseth like a bell, and comming neere the shore, presently is discovered a white tower or fort, which standeth upon the top of a hill over the harbour, and upon the seamost land. It is the first land a man must compasse before he enter the port. Comming within two leagues of the shore, we anchored; and the captaynes and masters of my other ships being come aboard, it was thought convenient (the weaknes of our men considered, for wee had not in our three ships twenty foure men sound), and the winde uncertaine when it might change, we thought with pollicie to procure that which wee could not by force; and so to offer traffique to the people of the shore; by that meanes to prove if wee could attayne some refreshing for our sicke company.

p.77

In execution whereof, I wrote a letter to the governour in Latine, and sent him with it a peece of crymson velvet, a bolt of fine holland, with divers other things, as a present; and with it, the captaine of my ship, who spake a little broken Spanish, giving the governour to understand that I was bound to the East Indies, to traffique in those parts, and that contrary windes had forced me upon that coast: if that hee were pleased to like of it, for the commodities the country yeilded in aboundance, I would exchange that which they wanted. With these instructions my captaine departed about nine of the clocke in the morning, carrying a flagge of truce in the head of the boate, and sixteene men well armed, and provided; guided by one of my company which two yeares before had bene captaine in that place, and so was a reasonable pilot.

p.78

Entering the port, within a quarter of a mile is a small village, and three leagues higher up is the chief towne; where they have two forts, one on eyther side of the harbour, and within them ride the ships which come thither to discharge, or loade. In the small village is ever a

garrison of one hundreth souldiers, whereof part assist there continually, and in the white tower upon the top of the hill, which commaundeth it.

Heere my captaine had good entertainment, and those of the shore received his message and letter, dispatching it presently to the governour, who was some three leagues off in another place: at least they beare us so in hand. In the time that they expected the post, my captaine with one other entertained himselfe with the souldiers a shore, who after the common custome of their profession (except when they be *besonios*)²⁷, sought to pleasure him, and finding that he craved but oranges, lemmons, and matters of smal moment for refreshing for his generall, they suffered the women and children to bring him what hee would, which hee gratified with double pistolets, that I had given him for that purpose. So got hee us two or three hundreth oranges and lemmons, and some fewe hennes.

p.79

All that day and night, and the next day, till nine of the clocke, wee waited the returne of our boate; which not appearing, bred in me some suspition; and for my satisfaction, I manned a light horseman which I had, and the *Fancie*, the best I could, shewing strength where was weaknesse and infirmity, and so set sayle towards the port; our gunner taking upon him to bee pilot, for that he had beene there some yeares before.

Thus, with them we entred the harbour. My captaine having notice of our being within the barre, came aboard with the boat, which was no small joy to me; and more, to see him bring us store of oranges and lemmons, which was that we principally sought for, as the remedie of our diseased company. He made relation of that had past, and how they expected present answer from the governour. We anchored right against the village; and within two houres, by a flagge of truce, which they on the shore shewed us, we understood that the messenger was come: our boat went for the answer of the governour, who said, he was sorry that he could not accomplish our desire, being so reasonable and good; for that in consideration of the warre betwixt Spaine and England, he had expresse order from his king, not to suffer any English to trade within his jurisdiction, no, nor to land, or to take any refreshing upon the shore. And therefore craved pardon, and that wee should take this for a resolute answer: and further required us to depart the port within three dayes, which he said he

27 Footnote in the 1847 reprint: (Spanish) raw, undisciplined.

gave us for our courteous manner of proceeding. If any of my people from that time forwards, should approach to the shore, that he would doe his best to hinder and annoy them. With this answer we resolved to depart; and before it came, with the first faire wind we determined to be packing; but the wind suffered us not all that night, nor the next day. In which time, I lived in a great perplexitie, for that I knew our own weaknesse, and what they might doe unto us, if that they had knowne so much. For any man that putteth himself into the enemies port, had need of Argus eyes, and the wind in a bagge, especially where the enemy is strong, and the tydes of any force. For with either ebbe or flood, those who are on the shore may thrust upon him inventions of fire: and with swimming or other devises, may cut his cables. A common practise in all hot countries. The like may be effected with raffles, cannoas, boates, or pynaces, to annoy and assault him: and **if this had beene practised against us, or taken effect, our shippes must of force have yeilded themselves; for they had no other people in them but sicke men;** but many times opinion and feare preserveth the shippes, and not the people in them.

For prevention of annoyances, etc., in harbours.

Wherefore it is the part of a provident governour, to consider well the daungers that may befall him, before he put himselfe into such places; so shall he ever be provided for prevention.

In Saint John de Vlva, in the New Spaine, when the Spanyards dishonoured their nation with that foule act of perjury, and breach of faith, given to my father, Sir John Hawkins (notorious to the whole world), the Spanyards fired two great shippes, with intention to burne my fathers Admirall, which he prevented by towing them with his boates another way.

The great armado of Spaine, sent to conquer England, anno 1588, was with that selfe same industry overthrowne; for the setting on fire of six or seaven shippes (whereof two were mine), and letting them drive with the flood, forced them to cut their cables, and to put to sea, to seeke a new way to Spaine. In which the greatest part of their best shippes and men were lost and perished.

For that my people should not be dismayed, I dispatched presently my light horsman, with onely foure men, and

part of the refreshing, advising them that with the first calme or slent of wind, they should come off.

The next night, the wind comming off the shore, wee set sayle, and with our boates and barkes sounded as we went.

It flowed upon the barre not above foure foote water, and once in foure and twentie houres, as in some parts of the West Indies; at full sea, there is not upon the barre above seventeen or eighteen foote water. The harbour runneth to the south-westwards. He that will come into it, is to open the harbour's mouth a good quarter of a league before he beare with it, and be bolder of the wester side; for of the easterland lyeth a great ledge of rocks, for the most part, under water, which sometimes break not; but with small shipping, a man may goe betwixt them and the poynt.

The vertue of oranges.

Comming aboard of our shippes, there was great joy amongst my company; and many, with the sight of the oranges and lemmons, seemed to recover heart. This is a wonderfull secret of the power and wisdome of God, that hath hidden so great and unknowne vertue in this fruit, to be a certaine remedie for this infirmitie; I presently caused them all to be reparted amongst our sicke men, which were so many, that there came not above three or foure to a share: but God was pleased to send us a prosperous winde the next day, so much to our comfort, that not any one dyed before we came to the ilands, where we pretended to refresh ourselves; and although our fresh water had fayled us many dayes before we saw the shore, by reason of our long navigation, without touching any land, and the excessive drinking of the sicke and diseased, which could not be excused, yet with an invention I had in my shippe,

p.82

Distilling of salt water.

I easily drew out of the water of the sea, sufficient quantitie of fresh water to sustaine my people with little expence of fewell; for with foure billets I stilled a hogshhead of water, and therewith dressed the meat for the sicke and whole. The water so distilled, we found to be wholesome and nourishing.

...

SECTION XXIV.

<https://archive.org/details/observationsofsi00hawk/page/84/mode/2up>

The next day about tenne of the clocke, wee were thwart of Cape Blanco, which is low sandie land, and perilous; for foure leagues into the sea (thwart it), lye banks of sand, which have little water on them; on a sudden we found our selves amongst them, in lesse then three fathome water; but with our boat and shalope we went sounding, and so got cleare of them.

p.85

The next day following, we discovered the ilands where wee purposed to refresh ourselves. They are two, and some call them Saint James, his ilands, and others, Saint Annes. They lie in two and twenty degrees and a halfe to the south-wards of the lyne; and towards the evening (being the fifth of November) we anchored betwixt them and the mayne, in six fathome water, where wee found our other shippes.

All which being well moored, we presently began to set up tents and booths for our sicke men, to carry them a shore, and to use our best diligence to cure them. For which intent our three surgeans, with their servants and adherents, had two boates to wayte continually upon them, to fetch whatsoever was needfull from the shippes, to procure refreshing, and to fish, either with netts, or hookes and lynes. Of these implements wee had in abundance, and it yeilded us some refreshing. For the first dayes, the most of those which had health, occupied themselves in romeging our ship; in bringing ashore of emptie caske; in filling of them, and in felling and cutting of wood: which being many workes, and few hands, went slowly forwards.

p.86

Neere these ilands, are two great rockes, or small ilands adjoyning. In them we found great store of young gannetts in their nests, which we reserved for the sicke, and being boyled with pickled porke well watered, and mingled with oatmeale, made reasonable pottage, and was good refreshing and sustenance for them. This provision fayled us not, till our departure from them.

Upon one of these rocks also, we found great store of the hearbe purslane, which boyled and made into sallets, with oyle and vineger, refreshed the sicke stomaches, and gave appetite.

With the ayre of the shore, and good cherishing, many recovered speedily.²⁸ Some died away quickly, and others continued at a stand. We found here some store of fruits; a kind of cherry that groweth upon a tree like a plum-tree, red of colour, with a stone in it, but different in making to ours, for it is not altogether round, and dented about: they have a pleasing taste.

In one of the ilands, we found palmito trees, great and high, and in the toppe a certaine fruit like cocos, but no bigger then a wall-nut. We found also a fruit growing upon trees in codd, like beanes, both in the codd and the fruit. Some of my company proved of them, and they caused vomits and purging, as any medicine taken out of the apothecaries shop, according to the quantitie received. They have hudds, as our beanes, which shaled off; the kernell parteth itselpe in two, and in the middle is a thin skinne, like that of an onion, said to be hurtfull, and to cause exceeding vomits, and therefore to be cast away.

Monardus writing of the nature and propertie of this fruit, as of others of the Indies, for that it is found in other parts, also calleth them *kavas purgativas*, and sayth, that they are to be prepared by peeling them first, and then taking away the skinne in the middle, and after beaten into powder, to take the quantitie of five or six, either with wine or sugar. Thus they are good against fevers, and to purge grosse humors; against the collicke, and payne of the joynts; in taking them a man may not sleepe, but is to use the dyet usuall, as in a day of purging.

One other fruit we found, very pleasant in taste, in fashion of an artechoque, but lesse; on the outside of colour redd, within white, and compassed about with prickles; our people called them pricke-pears; no conserve is better. They grow upon the leaves of a certaine roote, that is like unto that which we call *semper viva* and many are wont to hang them up in their houses; but their leaves are longer and narrower, and full of prickes on either side. The fruit groweth upon the side of the leafe, and is one of the best fruites that I have eaten in the Indies. In ripening, presently the birds or vermine are feeding on them;

A good note to take or refuse unknowne fruits.
a generall rule to know what fruit is wholesome and good in the Indies, and other parts. Finding them to be eaten of the beastes or fowles, a man may boldly eate of them.

p.87

28 Evidently, it was not air, but the plant foods that led to recovery.

The water of these ilands is not good: the one, for being a standing water, and full of venemous wormes and ser-pents, which is neare a butt-shot from the sea shore; where we found a great tree fallen, and in the roote of it the names of sundry Portingalls, Frenchmen, and others, and amongst them, Abraham Cockes; with the time of their being in this island.

p.88

The other, though a running water, yet passing by the rootes of certaine trees, which have a smell as that of gar-lique, taketh a certaine contagious sent of them. Here two of our men dyed with swelling of their bellies. The accident we could not attribute to any other cause, then to this suspitious water. It is little, and falleth into the sand, and soketh through it into the sea; and therefore we made a well of a pipe, and placeth it under the rocke from which it falleth, and out of it filled our caske: but we could not fill above two tunnes in a night and day.

SECTION XXV.

So after our people began to gather their strength, wee manned our boates, and went over to the mayne, where presently we found a great ryver of fresh and sweete water, and a mightie marish countrie; which in the winter seemeth to be continually over-flowne with this river, and others, which fall from the mountaynous country adjacent.

We rowed some leagues up the ryver, and found that the further up we went, the deeper was the river, but no fruit, more then the sweate of our bodies for the labour of our handes.

At our returne, wee loaded our boate with water, and afterwarde from hence wee made our store.

SECTION XXVI.

<https://archive.org/details/observationsofsi00hawk/page/88/mode/2up>

Wast and losse of men.

p.89

The sicknesse having wasted more then the one halfe of my people, we determined to take out the victualls of the *Hawke*, and to burne her; which wee put in execution.

And being occupied in this worke, we saw a shippe turning to windwards, to succour her selfe of the ilands; but having discryed us, put off to sea-wards.

Two dayes after, the wind changing, we saw her againe running alongst the coast, and the *Daintie* not being in case to goe after her, for many reasons, we manned the *Fancie*, and sent her after her; who about the setting of the sunne fetched her up, and spake with her; when finding her to be a great fly-boat, of at least three or foure hundreth tunnes, with eighteen peeces of artillery, would have returned, but the wind freshing in, put her to lee-wards; and standing in to succour her selfe of the land, had sight of another small barke, which after a short chase shee tooke, but had nothing of moment in her, for that she had bin upon the great sholes of Abreoios, in eighteen degrees, and there throwne all they had by the board, to save their lives.

This and the other chase were the cause that the *Fancie* could not beat it up in many dayes: but before we had put all in a readinesse, the wind changing, shee came unto us, and made relation of that which had past; and how they had given the small barke to the Portingalls, and brought with them onely her pilot, and a marchant called Pedro de Escalante of Potosi.

This is a selection of more relevant sections of the Editor's Preface (1847), see the entire Preface at:

<https://www.gutenberg.org/ebooks/57502>

<https://archive.org/details/dli.ministry.04871/page/n5/mode/2up>

EDITOR'S PREFACE (1847)

MANY of the early voyages to the Spanish possessions in South America, are open to the charge of having been conducted more upon buccaneering principles, than on those that should guide nations in their intercourse with each other.

p.vii

Even Sir Francis Drake, on his return from one of the most memorable, endured the mortification of being considered little better than a pirate, and it required all the honors conferred on him by Queen Elizabeth, to set him right in public opinion. This is not the proper place to discuss the question, whether England was justified in allowing such expeditions to leave her shores; it is sufficient to state, that our author is not liable to any animadversion, as his voyage was undertaken under the authority of the Queen's commission; and his conduct was marked throughout by humanity and benevolence.

p.viii

We can hardly appreciate too highly the adventurous daring of these early navigators; but while we give due credit to them for attempting such long voyages into almost unknown seas, in vessels of small burthen, we must not imagine that they were utterly unprovided for the nature of the expected service: on the contrary, great care seems have been taken both in selecting proper crews, and in providing them with everything needful.

Sir Richard Hawkins, at page 12, alludes generally to his own preparations; and we read in the accounts of Sir Francis Drake's expedition, "that his vessels were plentifully furnished with all manner of provisions and necessaries for so long and dangerous a voyage; and such as served only for ornament and delight were likewise not forgotten. For this purpose he took with him very expert musicians for several instruments. His furniture of all kinds was rich and sumptuous; all the vessels for his

table, and many in the cook-room, being of pure silver, curiously wrought, and many other things whereby the magnificence of his native country might be displayed.”

...

Sir Richard Hawkins followed the profession of a seaman from an early age. Brought up in stirring times, under the eye of his father, one of the most experienced naval commanders of his time, he appears to have inherited a knowledge of sound principles of discipline, and to have become imbued with that indomitable courage, tempered with prudence, essential to the character of a good sea officer. In 1588, Captain Hawkins commanded the *Swallow*, a Queen’s ship of three hundred and sixty tons, and assisted in her at the destruction of the Spanish armada. He appears at that period to have attained a certain consideration, as he was employed as Queen’s Commissioner, to settle some prize claims. He next undertook the voyage the history of which is recounted in the following pages. After his return from his detention in the South Seas, we find him, in 1620, in the *Vanguard*, of six hundred and sixty tons, vice-admirall of Sir Robert Mansel’s expedition against the Algerines. He died suddenly shortly afterwards.

p.xiv

p.xv

Admiral Burney, in his *History of Voyages and Discoveries in the South Seas*, alluding to this work, says, “it might with propriety have been entitled a book of good counsel; many of his observations being unconnected with the voyage he is relating, but his digressions are ingenious and entertaining, and they frequently contain useful or curious information”: and Mr. Barrow, in his *Memoirs of the Naval Worthies of Queen Elizabeth*, thinks that the “*Observations must take their station in the very first rank of our old sea voyages.*”

Similar considerations led the council of the Hakluyt Society²⁹ to select it, though not exactly a rare work, for early publication; and it is submitted to the Members, with a confident hope that it will repay an attentive perusal.

29 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Hakluyt_Society
<https://www.hakluyt.com>

The editor has confined his labours to reproducing the text of the original, with only such slight alterations as were necessary where the sense of the author had been obviously marred by a misprint; giving such explanations of obsolete words and technical terms as might embarrass an unprofessional reader; identifying the places visited with their modern appellation, where practicable; and adding such remarks as occurred to him while correcting the proof sheets.

p.xvi

C. R. D. B. [C.R. Drinkwater Bethune, Captain R.N.]
Nov. 1847.

This 1878 introduction gives a biography of the Hawkinses.
There are footnotes in the original text, but they are not copied here.
See the original version at:

<https://archive.org/details/hawkinsvoyagesdu00markrich/page/n15/mode/2up>

INTRODUCTION (1878) by Clements Markham

THE *Observations of Sir Richard Hawkins in his Voyage into the South Sea* was the first volume issued by the Hakluyt Society, in 1847.³⁰ It was edited by Admiral C. R. Drinkwater Bethune, C.B.; and most of his valuable foot-notes in the first edition have been retained, especially those explaining old sea terms and Spanish phrases. Some of the Admiral's notes have been omitted as having become obsolete, or from other considerations. As the first edition is now out of print, it has become necessary to reproduce it. The Council decided that the present volume should be made more complete, by including the narratives of the voyages of Sir Richard's grandfather William, of his father Sir John, and of his cousin William Hawkins. It is, therefore, intended to be a monograph of the naval enterprises of the great Elizabethan navigators of the name of Hawkins.

p.i

The first of that name made three voyages to Brazil in the time of Henry VIII, and was one of our earliest naval pioneers. The second was closely connected with the history of our navy, both as a gallant commander at sea and as an able administrator on shore, during upwards of thirty eventful years. The third was a worthy emulator of his father's fame; while the fourth is among the first founders of the success of the East India Company.

p.ii

The cradle of the naval Hawkinses was certainly in Devonshire, the county of Drake and Oxenham, of Grenville and Davis, of Raleigh and Gilbert, and of so many other Elizabethan naval worthies. In the reign of Henry VII, John Hawkins and his wife Joan, daughter of William Amydas of Launceston, were living at Tavistock, and their son William Hawkins is the first of the three generations of famous seamen.

30 <https://www.gutenberg.org/ebooks/57502>

We owe our slight knowledge of the first **WILLIAM HAWKINS**³¹ to the research of Hakluyt.³² He tells us that old Mr. William Hawkins of Plymouth was a man of wisdom, valour, experience, and skill in sea causes, and that he was much esteemed and beloved by King Henry VIII. He was one of the principal sea captains in the west of England in his time, and made three adventurous voyages to the coast of Brazil, an account of two of which, taken from Hakluyt, will be found at pages 3 and 4 of the present volume. William Hawkins married Joan, daughter of William Trelawney, and had two sons, John and William, who entered upon the sea service with great advantages, owing to the wealth and experience of their father.

p.iii

The date of the birth of **JOHN HAWKINS**³³ is not certain, but the inscription on his monument, formerly in the church of St. Dunstan's-in-the-East, gives his age at the time of his death in 1595, as "six times ten and three". If this is correct, he was born in 1532. Hakluyt tells us that he made divers voyages to the Canary Islands in his youth, where he obtained much information respecting the trade with the West Indies. He heard, among other things, that there was a great demand for negroes at St. Domingo, and that they could easily be obtained from the coast of Guinea. He resolved to make trial of this trade, and, having communicated his plan to several influential friends in London, he received liberal support. Among those who were adventurers for this voyage, was Mr. Benjamin Gonson, of Sebright Hall, near Chelmsford, and Treasurer of the Navy, who, probably before the ship sailed, became the father-in-law of the gallant young-commander of the expedition.

John Hawkins, when he undertook the voyage in 1562, was in about his thirtieth year; and he was then married to Katharine Gonson, daughter of the Treasurer of the Navy, by whom he had a son Richard.

p.iv

31 [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/William_Hawkins_\(died_c._1554\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/William_Hawkins_(died_c._1554))
<https://www.historyofparliamentonline.org/volume/1509-1558/member/hawkins-william-1495-155455>

32 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Richard_Hakluyt

33 [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/John_Hawkins_\(naval_commander\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/John_Hawkins_(naval_commander))
<https://www.historyofparliamentonline.org/volume/1558-1603/member/hawkins-john-1532-95>
"one of the foremost seamen of 16th-century England and the chief architect of the Elizabethan navy."
<https://www.britannica.com/biography/John-Hawkins-English-naval-commander>

The first expedition of John Hawkins, consisting of three good ships, was very successful, though a cargo which he sent to Cadiz in charge of his second in command, Captain Hampton, was confiscated. An order was also sent to the Indies, by the Spanish Government, that no English vessel was to be allowed to trade there in future. The account of this voyage, taken from Hakluyt, will be found from pages 5 to 7 of the present volume. Hawkins returned in September 1563.

No blame attaches to the conduct of John Hawkins in undertaking a venture which all the world, in those days, looked upon as legitimate and even as beneficial. It was in 1517 that Charles V issued royal licences for the importation of negroes into the West Indies, and in 1551 a licence for importing 17,000 negroes was offered for sale. The measure was adopted from philanthropic motives, and was intended to preserve the Indians. It was looked upon as prudent and humane, even if it involved some suffering on the part of a far inferior race. The English were particularly eager to enter upon the slave trade, and by the treaty of Utrecht in 1713 England at length obtained the *asiento*, giving her the exclusive right to carry on the slave trade between Africa and the Spanish Indies for thirty years. So strong was the party in favour of this trade in England, that the contest for its abolition was continued for forty-eight years, from 1759 to 1807. It is not, therefore, John Hawkins alone who can justly be blamed for the slave trade, but the whole English people during 250 years, who must all divide the blame with him.

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John Hawkins sailed on his second voyage in 1564, in the good ship *Jesus of Lubeck*, of 700 tons, returning in the autumn of the following year. He was accompanied by several gentlemen adventurers, and one of them, named John Sparke, wrote the narrative published by Hakluyt. It will be found from pages 8 to 64 of the present volume, and is followed by an account of the succour given by Hawkins to a distressed French colony in Florida, which Hakluyt translated from the French work of M. Laudonnière, printed in Paris in 1586. Mr. Sparke is somewhat diffuse, but he gives many interesting details respecting the various places, in Africa and the West Indies, that

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were touched at, including a full account of Florida.

The third voyage was undertaken in 1567, and had a most disastrous termination. It was on this occasion that Hawkins and Francis Drake first served together. Drake is called the kinsman of Hawkins by his biographers, and he certainly appears to have been born in a cottage on the banks of the Tavy, while the Hawkinses came originally from Tavistock, so that the two families were near neighbours. Francis was about ten years younger than Hawkins. His father was persecuted under the Six Articles Act, and fled into Kent, where he became the vicar of Upnor, and the son served his apprenticeship in the Medway, and in short voyages to Zeeland. But young Francis, as soon as he had the means, returned to his native county, and had made at least one voyage (with Captain Lovell in 1565-66) to the West Indies before he joined the expedition of Hawkins. The latter commanded his old ship, the *Jesus of Lubeck*, while Drake was in a little vessel called the *Judith* (of 50 tons). The sad story of this voyage, as given in Hakluyt, was written by John Hawkins himself, and will be found from pages 70 to 81 of the present volume. After the treacherous attack of the Spaniards at San Juan de Ulloa, two vessels only escaped, the *Minion*, with Hawkins on board, and the *Judith*; but there was not sufficient food for so large a number of men crowded into two small vessels, and their case seemed almost hopeless. At length half the number, a hundred out of two hundred, volunteered to land on the coast of Mexico, so as to save the rest. They were put on shore, and their more fortunate comrades, after suffering great hardships, arrived in England on January 25th, 1568.

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It is remarkable that Hawkins never mentions Drake's name throughout his narrative. His letter to Mr. Secretary Cecil, describing his misfortunes, is dated on the day of his landing in Mounts Bay.

The fate of the unfortunate men who were put on shore in Mexico was most cruel. They were sent to the capital, and were at first treated with humanity. But in 1571 a tribunal of the Inquisition was established in Mexico, the English castaways were seized and shockingly maltreated, and several tortured and most inhumanly mutilated. Some were burnt, and a few were sent to Spain, and left to die of hunger in

the Archbishop of Seville's dungeons. Three escaped, and the tale of their wrongs excited the utmost indignation throughout England. The narratives of these survivors, David Ingram, Job Hartop, and Miles Philips, are given by Hakluyt; and no one who peruses them can be surprised at the hatred of the English against the Spaniards in those days. John Hawkins was extremely anxious about the fate of his unhappy men, and when tidings of their treatment began to reach England he sought every means to be revenged upon the Spanish nation. He intended to go out in search of his men, but was prevented. He then determined to try what cunning would do, apparently deeming intrigue and deceit to be justifiable against such a foe.

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But there never was a more absurd calumny than that promulgated by Dr. Lingard and others, to the effect that Hawkins consented to betray his country for a bribe from Spain. Lingard refers us to an agreement made at Madrid on August 10th, 1571, between the Duke of Feria, on the part of Philip II, and George Fitzwilliam on the part of John Hawkins, by which the latter was to transfer his services to Spain, bringing with him sixteen of the Queen's ships fully equipped with 420 guns, in consideration of an amnesty for past offences, and monthly pay of 16,987 ducats. This pretended agreement may be found in the Spanish Archives. The calumny lies in Dr. Lingard's conclusion from it, and in his additional statements which are as follows. "The secret was carefully kept, but did not elude suspicion. Hawkins was summoned, and examined by order of the Council. Their lordships were, or pretended to be, satisfied, and he was engaged in the Queen's service." Lingard adds that Hawkins tendered hostages to Spain for his fidelity. All these supplementary statements are untrue. The simple fact was that Hawkins was trying to deceive and entrap the Spaniards, with the full knowledge and approval of the English Government from the first. This is proved beyond doubt by Cecil's correspondence. It was not very clean work and it ended in failure, but it is false that Hawkins was ever untrue to his country. A more loyal and devoted subject never lived. His whole life was one of zealous devotion to the service of his Queen. His Spanish intrigue was

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undertaken with the object of rescuing his unfortunate men by a resort to guile, as he could not do so by force. Their miserable condition must have haunted him, and he felt that any means that offered a chance of liberating them was justifiable.

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After his three voyages, John Hawkins justly stood high with the Government, as a resolute and experienced sea captain. In 1565 a coat of arms was granted to him, with an augmentation in August 1571.

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In 1573 Hawkins succeeded his father-in-law as Treasurer of the Navy, and commenced a useful, but very anxious and laborious administrative career on shore. But he still occasionally served afloat. In 1570 his son tells us that he was Admiral of the fleet of Queen's ships then riding in Catwater, and that he fired upon a Spanish ship for not lowering her topsails. In a letter dated February 23rd, 1573, from Charles IX to La Motte Fénelon, a complaint is made against "Haquin" (Hawkins) for being joined with certain French rebels in the neighbourhood of the Isle of Wight, to the number of twelve or thirteen ships, with which they carried munitions and provisions from England to Rochelle.

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The civil employments of John Hawkins must, however, have absorbed most of his time. Besides the Treasurership of the Navy, he was also Treasurer of the Queen's Majesty's Marine Causes, and in the same year he succeeded Mr. Holstock as Comptroller of the Navy. He was a keen reformer of dockyard abuses, and Sir William Monson says that he introduced more useful inventions and better regulations into the navy than any of his predecessors. Stow tells us that Hawkins was the first that invented the cunning stratagem of sail nettings for ships in fighting, and he also devised chain pumps for ships.

In 1581 he had a severe illness, but he had recovered in 1583, when we find him busily engaged making investigations for the reduction of the expenses of the navy, and encountering much opposition. For fifteen months the officers at Chatham took "hardness and courage to oppose themselves against him", yet he there made a saving of over £3,200, while adding to the efficiency of the fleet. His correspondence with Sir Julius Caesar, the Judge of the Admiralty, shows that

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he paid close attention to all branches of naval expenditure, detecting and putting a stop to many abuses. This good service naturally made him enemies. Mr. Borowe, who was ousted, “made a book against him”, and in 1583 there were articles drawn up “against the injuste mind and deceitful dealings of John Hawkins”. Among those whom he found out conniving at abuses were Sir William Winter and the Master Shipwright Baker, who of course became his bitter enemies, and he had a controversy with Mr. Peter Pett, the shipwright, touching his accounts. Winter wrote —“When he was hurte in the Strande and made his will he was not able to give £500. All that he is now worth hath byn drawne by decepte from her Majesty.” These calumnies received no credit, and Hawkins never lost the confidence of his Government.

In 1584 we find him consulting with Peter Pett as to a project for improving Dover harbour. In December 1585 he submitted books to Lord Burleigh with lists of her Majesty’s ships, their tonnage, and estimates for outfit; and he represented the expediency of increasing the seamen’s pay. He also sent in a statement of the management of the navy from 1568 to 1579, with his scheme for its future government by commissioners.

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During all these years of active civil employment John Hawkins lived in a house in the parish of St. Dunstan’s-in-the-East, with his office at Deptford. He lost his first wife, the mother of his son, when she was only thirty-two years of age, and married secondly Margaret, daughter of Charles Vaughan, Esq., of Hergest House, Herefordshire, by Elizabeth, daughter of Sir F. Baskerville. This lady was bed-chamber woman to the Queen.

In 1587 the intention of Spain to invade England was manifest, and a Council consisting of Lord Charles Howard, Hawkins, Drake, and Frobisher, got the English fleet in readiness to meet its formidable adversary. Hawkins was appointed Vice-Admiral, hoisting his flag on board the *Victory*; and after the dispersion of the Spanish Armada he received the honour of knighthood. Then came the anxious and troublesome business of paying off the fleet. “I pray God”, he wrote to Burleigh, “I may end this account to her Majesty’s and your Lordship’s liking, and avoyd myne

owne undoing, and I trust God will so provyde for me as I shall never meddell with soche intrycate matters more.” In 1590 he got away to sea again, in a fleet commanded by himself and Sir Martin Frobisher, with orders to do all possible mischief on the coast of Spain. But the Plate fleet was warned in time, and remained in the Indies. None of the enemy’s ships appeared, and the expedition came back without any results. Sir John Hawkins, on his return, reminded Elizabeth that “Paul planteth and Apollos watereth, but God giveth the increase.” “God’s death!” exclaimed the Queen, “this fool went out a soldier, and is come home a divine!”

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In the year 1588 Sir John, aided by Drake, instituted a fund for maimed and worn out mariners, which was long known as the “chest at Chatham”. This fund was the forerunner of Greenwich Hospital. Thus actively and laboriously employed, on shore and afloat, Sir John Hawkins became grey in the service of his country. Edmund Spenser, when he drew likenesses of the chief sea captains of England, in his “*Colin Clout’s come home again*”, speaks of old Hawkins as Proteus, “with hoary head and dewy dropping beard”. His end was heroic. In 1593 he had, with some difficulty, obtained a commission for his dearly loved son Richard, when he set out on his adventurous voyage to the South Sea in the good ship *Dainty*. Then came the sad news that his boy was a prisoner in the hands of the Spaniards.

There can be no doubt that old Sir John undertook his last fatal voyage with a broken heart, in the faint hope of rescuing his son.

An expedition was decided upon to sail for the West Indies under the command of Sir John Hawkins and Sir Francis Drake, in 1595. The Queen furnished five ships, but she drove a hard bargain with her old Treasurer of the Navy. She was to have a third of the booty, and Sir John was to victual the fleet at his own charge. He did his part well, being, as Sir T. Gorges reported from Plymouth to Robert Cecil, “an excellent man in those things, and sees all things done orderly.” Nombre de Dios was the destination of the fleet, but Hawkins died at sea, off Puerto Rico, on the 21st of November 1595.

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So ended the life of Sir John Hawkins, one of the best of Elizabeth's great sea captains, and the terror of the Spaniards. He was a thorough seaman, and an able and upright administrator; endowed with great courage and unflinching presence of mind; "merciful," says Maynarde, "and apt to forgive, and faithful to his word". Stow, in his *Chronicle*, speaks of him as a very wise, vigilant, and true-hearted man.

On July 9th, 1596, the disbursements of Sir John Hawkins in his last voyage, were delivered by Robert Langford, Deputy Treasurer, in the name of his widow Margeret Hawkins, at £18,661, which was declared to be not more than his third part. His watery grave was far away within the tropics, but a handsome tomb to his memory was erected on the north side of the chancel of St. Dunstan's-in-the-East, which was his place of worship during many years. It bore the following inscription...

There is a basso-relievo ivory bust of Sir John Hawkins in the possession of the Reverend Bradford Denne Hawkins, Rector of Rivenhall, near Witham, in Essex, who informs me that it came to his father by inheritance, from Dr. Denne, Archdeacon of Rochester and Rector of Lambeth in the last century.

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I can only hear of one portrait of Sir John Hawkins. It was at Kirtling in Cambridgeshire, the seat of the Lords North, and on the dismantling of the house in 1802 it was sold. In 1824 it came into the hands of a Mr. Bryant, whose brother sold it to Mr. R. S. Hawkins of Oxford in 1866. It is a portrait on panel, kit-cat size, of a man in armour, with small head, dark brown hair and yellowish beard, and the hand resting on a helmet. The face has a strong family resemblance to that of the ivory basso-relievo bust. Above the shoulder of the figure are reeds, a rock, and waves, and the following motto... The present owner inclines to the belief that it is a portrait of the son Sir Richard, and not of Sir John Hawkins.

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The will of Sir John Hawkins was proved in December 1596.

RICHARD HAWKINS, the only son of Sir John, was brought up to a sea life from a boy, and his father's position and circumstances must have given him special advantages. For his father and uncle, the two brothers John and William, were men of considerable means, at one time owning thirty sail of good ships. Richard was born at about the time of his father's first Guinea voyage in 1562. His mother died when she was only thirty-two, so that the boy became his father's constant companion at an early age, and his reminiscences went back to a childhood spent at Plymouth and Deptford, amongst ships and dockyards. Thus, in his *Observations*, he calls to mind how, he being of tender years, there came a large fleet of Spaniards into Plymouth Sound, bound for Flanders to fetch Queen Anne of Austria, last wife of Phillip II. "They entred without vaying their top-sayles or taking in of their flags; which my father Sir John Hawkins (Admiral of a fleet of her Majesties ships then ryding in Cattwater) perceiving, commanded his gunner to shoote at the flagge of the Admirall, that they might thereby see their error; which, notwithstanding, they persevered arrogantly to keepe displayed, whereupon the gunner at the next shot, lact the admiral through and through, whereby the Spaniards tooke in the flags and top-sayles, and so ramie to anchor." In this masterful school was young Richard Hawkins brought up. At the age of twenty, "being but young and more bold than experimented", he made his first long voyage to the West Indies in 1582, with his uncle William Hawkins of Plymouth. During the voyage he displayed boldness and sagacity which showed that he had the makings of a good officer and seaman. On one occasion the captain of one of the vessels named the *Bonner* reported her to be leaky and unseaworthy, and it was arranged that the stores and provisions should be taken out of her, the men divided among the other ships, and the hull sunk or burnt. Richard suspected that the captain of the *Bonner* made the matter worse than it really was. So he volunteered, with as many men as would stand by him, to take her home, and his uncle consented; but this shamed the captain, who resolved to stand by her. Thus he saved the vessel to the owners, and was commended for his resolution. During the voyage he

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visited the Margarita pearl fishery.

From his return in 1583 to the equipment of the fleet to withstand the Spanish Armada in 1588, Richard Hawkins was constantly employed on sea service. His father had married again, as already mentioned, to a lady of whom her step-son speaks as “religious and most virtuous and of very good understanding”; so that his home relations were probably undisturbed. In 1588 he commanded the *Swallow* in the fleet which opposed the Spanish Armada; and in the end of the same year, with the consent and help of his father, he prepared for a voyage to China and India by way of the straits of Magellan and the South Sea, with the object of discovering and surveying unknown lands, and reporting upon their inhabitants, governments, and on the commodities they yield, and of which they are in want. With this object he caused a ship to be built in the Thames, between 300 and 400 tons, “pleasing to the eye, profitable for stowage, good of sayle, and well-conditioned.” His step-mother craved the naming of the ship and called her the *Repentance*. Richard often asked her reason for bestowing upon his ship so uncouth a name, but he could never get any other satisfaction than that “*Repentance* was the safest ship we could sayle in, to purchase the haven of heaven”. Queen Elizabeth afterwards passed by, on her way to Greenwich Palace, and, causing her bargemen to row round the ship, disliked nothing but her name. She christened her anew, and ordered that henceforth she should be called the *Daintie*.³⁴ Other duties delayed the voyage, and in the meanwhile the *Daintie* was usefully, employed in the Queen’s service, but in April 1593 all things were in readiness, and the young adventurer prepared to sail on his great enterprise.

Richard Hawkins was now in about his thirtieth year; and he already had a wife and children. He had married a short time previously a lady whose Christian name was Judith, but I have not yet succeeded in ascertaining to what family she belonged. He was already an experienced sea captain, and had seen much service. He was a man of resource, observant and eager to adopt every new improvement or good suggestion. Devoted to his profession, his whole mind was wrapped up in its interests, he paid

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34 [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/English_ship_Dainty_\(1588\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/English_ship_Dainty_(1588))

close attention to every detail, and nothing seemed to escape him. Thus his *Observations* are a perfect storehouse of valuable information of all kinds, and every incident of the voyage leads him off into reminiscences of former experiences, or into statements of facts and observations gathered from others. The *Observations of Sir Richard Hawkins* will be found from pages 89 to 329 of the present volume.

On the 13th of June 1593, Richard Hawkins, having taken his unhappy last leave of his father, sailed from Plymouth on board the *Daintie*, accompanied by the *Fancy* pinnace of 60 tons, and a victualler named the *Hawk*. The most noteworthy event during the voyage across the Atlantic was the sighting of land of which Hawkins believed himself to be the first discoverer, and which he named "Hawkins's maiden-land". This was on the 2nd of February 1594, in latitude, according to Hawkins, about 49° 30' S. Hawkins wrote from memory, and fortunately he is corrected, as regards his latitude, by one of his officers named Ellis, who tells us that the land was in 50° S. and about fifty leagues off the Straits of Magellan. Without doubt they sighted the Falkland Islands, but the group had already been discovered by John Davis,³⁵

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the great Arctic Navigator, in August 1592. Davis reached Berehaven on June 11th, 1593, and Hawkins sailed from Plymouth on June 13th, so that Hawkins was not aware of the previous discovery. Passing through the Strait of Magellan, the *Daintie* ranged up the west coast of South America, encountered a Spanish fleet off Chilca, from which she was separated by a gale of wind, and anchored in the bay of Atacames on June 10th, 1594.

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Hawkins was now on the coast of the province of Quito, a little to the north of the equator. Atacames Bay is in 0° 57' 30" N. To the left is Cape San Francisco, off which Sir Francis Drake captured his rich prize the *Cacafuego* on March 1st, 1579. To the right is the mouth of the great river of Santiago, and the bay of San Mateo.

It is a coast which was much frequented by Dampier and the buccaneers in the end of the following century. On the 14th of June Hawkins was in the Bay of San

35 Scurvy occurred also on the voyage of John Davis
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17884408>

Mateo. On the 17th he was about to make sail and leave the coast of South America, when the Spanish fleet, under the command of Don Beltran de Castro, came round the point. Hawkins fought a most gallant action, and did not surrender until he had received several wounds, was quite over-matched, and the ship was sinking. He also gives a most spirited and interesting account of it, interspersed with remarks on naval discipline, gunnery, and seamanship. After three days' hard fighting the gallant young Englishman surrendered to superior force on the 22nd of June, 1594. The Spanish commander, Don Beltran de Castro, a humane and honorable man, granted quarter, and promised that Hawkins and his people should be allowed to return to their own country. Don Beltran received young Hawkins with great courtesy and kindness, and accommodated him in his own cabin. The prize was taken to Panama, where she arrived on the 9th of July, the distance from San Mateo being 500 miles, a very slow passage. She was re-christened the *Visitacion*.

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I have inserted, after the *Observations of Sir Richard Hawkins*, a Spanish account of the naval action between our hero and Don Beltran de Castro, which I have translated from the life of the Marquis of Canete, Viceroy of Peru, by Dr. Don Christobal Suarez de Figueroa. Readers will thus be able to form a judgment from the accounts of both sides. They agree on all material points. Hawkins wrote from memory, and many years after the event; while Suarez de Figueroa, although he was not an actor in the scenes he describes, had the great advantage of having at his disposal all the official and other documents formerly in the possession of the Viceroy of Peru at the time.

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Hawkins and his fellow prisoners were taken to Payta, and thence to Lima. Hawkins was at first treated with kindness and consideration by the Marquis of Canete, then Viceroy of Peru; and his servant Saunders says that he was beloved for his valour, by all brave men in those parts. He was received, says Saunders, by all the best of the country, and carried by them to a princely house all richly hanged, the which he had to himself. But afterwards he was claimed by the Inquisition, and suffered much anxiety and annoyance. The Viceroy delayed entire compliance

with the requisition of the Holy Office on the ground that he had no instructions. Nevertheless, within six or seven days of his arrival at Lima, Hawkins was carried by a Father to the “Holy House”, to rest there till they heard what should be done with him. The honour of Don Beltran de Castro, who had promised that Hawkins and his people should be allowed to return to England, was also compromised. The Marquis wrote to Philip II for orders, and received a very ambiguous reply, dated December 1595. The King wrote:— “You understand that he (Hawkins) is a person of quality. In this matter I desire that Justice may be done conformably to the quality of the persons.” This loop-hole probably enabled the Viceroy to defy the Inquisition, and Hawkins was sent to Spain, by way of Panama in 1597, after a detention of three years at Lima. Purchas gives two interesting extracts from letters written by fellow captives of Hawkins. The first is *A brief note written by Master John Ellis, one of the captains with Sir Richard Hawkins in his voyage through the Strait of Magellan, begunne the ninth of April 1593, concerning the said strait and certaine places on the coast and inland of Peru*. Ellis made a journey from Lima across the Andes to Guamanga and Cuzco. He was the first Englishman who ever visited the ancient capital of the Yncas,³⁶ which he describes as being as “big as Bristol, having a castle on a hill with stones of 20 tons weight strangely joined together without mortar”. Purchas next gives two letters from T. Saunders, servant to Sir Richard Hawkins, addressed to his father, Sir John, from the prison at San Lucar. Saunders speaks of one Master Lucas, who was condemned to the galleys by the Holy Office and sent to Nombre de Dios, where he died.

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Sir Richard was sent to Spain in a galleon which touched at Terceira, in the Azores. A fleet under the Earl of Essex chased her into the roads, and she did not escape without loss, for the splinters from the English shot killed and wounded a dozen Spaniards. The galleon, with Hawkins on board, then continued its voyage to Seville, and in the *Observations* there is an account of a curious accident which befell two ships at anchor in the river, owing to a Spanish punctilio.

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Sir Richard was thrown into prison at Seville, in

36 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Inca_Empire

defiance of the terms of his surrender, and was dishonourably detained for several years. Don Beltran de Castro was indignant at a breach of faith which compromised his honour, and persistently protested against it, but for a long time without avail. In May 1598 a letter to Cecil reported that Hawkins was still kept in the castle at San Lucar, as a hostage for Spaniards in England. Another letter from Lisbon reported that Captain Hawkins escaped out of the castle of Seville in September 1598, but was taken, thrust into a dungeon, and great store of irons put upon him. In the following year the unhappy captive managed to send a message to England. One Deacon, Sir Richard's servant, was passed over by Martin de Marseval from St. Jean de Luz, and enabled to get on board a British vessel of St. Ives in the Breton port of Conquet, in August 1599. In April 1600 Richard Cooke, another messenger, brought news of the captive, taking a passage in the *Diana* of Portsmouth.

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By one of these channels Hawkins made a touching appeal to Queen Elizabeth, his letter being dated April 1st, 1598. He wrote from his prison in Seville, asking for compassion in the name of his father's services, who sacrificed his life for his Queen. He added that he himself had spent fifteen years in her service without pay or recompense, knowing that she had infinite charges while he had a good estate; and he urged that he was in danger of perpetual imprisonment unless her powerful hand was reached out. The letter concludes with a piteous appeal in the name of his wife and children. In 1599 he was removed to Madrid.

His next letter is dated from the Court Prison at Madrid, on October 23rd, 1599, and addressed to Sir Henry Nevill, the English Ambassador at Paris. He tells him that he is the unfortunate son of Sir John Hawkins; that he fought for three days and nights and was wounded in six places; that most of his men were killed and wounded, and that he surrendered when the ship was ready to sink. The Spanish general sent his glove as a pledge to give life and liberty; but he had been detained lest he should return and molest the Spaniards. Most of his people had been freed long ago. He entreated the Ambassador to intercede with the Queen for him. "I and my father", he concluded, "ever since we could bear arms, spent time and sub-

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stance in her service.”

The dishonorable detention of Richard Hawkins at last excited the indignation of a more powerful man than Don Beltran de Castro. The credit of his release is due to the Count of Miranda, who declared, if a prisoner was detained whose liberty had been promised, no future agreement could ever be made, because faith in Spanish honour would be destroyed. His views prevailed, and Richard Hawkins at length returned to England, after a dreary captivity of nearly eight years.

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It was a sad home-coming. The brave old father gone, the estates of both ruined, and long years of the prime of life utterly wasted. Richard Hawkins settled down, with his wife and children, in one of the most secluded combes between Dartmouth³⁷ and the Start Point.³⁸ The road from Dartmouth to Slapton leads southwards along the coast, with the sea generally in sight, first up a very steep hill to Stoke Fleming, then down to the little hamlet of Blackpool in a shingly bay, up again to Street, and down to the long reach of Slapton Sands,³⁹ which extends for several miles, almost to the Start. The “sands” are in reality a steep bank of fine shingle, within which there is a fresh water lake called the Ley, about three miles long, full of roach and pike, and frequented by water fowl of all kinds. A causeway leads across the Ley and over the hill, down into the pretty little village of Slapton. The church has a low tower and spire, a nave separated from the two aisles by four arches, and good perpendicular windows. There is a very richly carved wooden rood screen across the chancel and others across each aisle, with grapes and vine leaves carved along the upper borders. Old glass from other windows has been collected in a south chancel window, consisting of coats of arms of the Bryan family (or three piles *azure*). Near the church, and in the hollow where the village is built, there is a tall ivy-covered tower of the fourteenth century, part of a chantry founded by Jane, the wife of Sir Guy de Bryan, K.G. Slapton was originally the property of the Bryan family. In the time of Henry VIII it was sold to Edward Ameredith, and his son

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37 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Dartmouth,_Devon

38 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Start_Point,_Devon

39 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Slapton,_Devon

John sold Slapton and Pole to Sir Richard Hawkins.

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From Slapton church a pretty Devonshire lane leads up for a quarter-of-a-mile to Pole, where is the site of the old residence of the Bryans, Amerediths, and Hawkinses, in a secluded hollow, with many fine trees. No ruins remain now, and the site is occupied by a modern house and farm buildings. From the lane leading down from Pole to Slapton there is a view of the sea, with Start Point in the distance. It was here that Sir Richard Hawkins lived during the last twenty years of his life, with his wife and family; passing down the lane to Slapton church every Sunday, and doubtless recounting his adventures and sufferings to friends and relations during many a summer stroll and winter evening in the old house at Pole.

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But Sir Richard Hawkins was very far from being an idle man in his Devonshire home. He was knighted by James I, was appointed Vice-Admiral of Devon, and was often at Plymouth on business connected with his office. In March 1605 we find him sequestering a Spanish prize laden with Brazil wood and sugar, which was driven into Salcombe bay. In June 1608 he is corresponding with the Earl of Nottingham respecting some pirates, and discussing a question of Admiralty jurisdiction; and in September of the same year mention is made of his active prosecution of pirates, in his office of Vice-Admiral of Devon.

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He was also engaged in projects for a new voyage of discovery. In March 1614 there was a proposal before the Governors of the East India Company for carrying out a favourite scheme of Sir James Lancaster to send a ship through Magellan's Straits to the Solomon Islands, and it was suggested that Sir Richard Hawkins should have the command. He was generally held to be of "courage, art, and knowledge" to attempt such enterprise. There is a letter from Sir Richard himself to the Company on this subject, dated July 16th, 1614. He referred to a discovery formerly made by him, and to his desire to undertake another voyage to the Straits in person. A Committee was appointed to confer with Sir James Lancaster on the subject, and then to treat with Sir Richard, but with orders not to meddle with his ship, which was very old. He offered, with others, to join the Company in adventuring

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£20,000 for a voyage to the South Sea.

Nothing appears to have come of this negotiation, which shows, however, that Hawkins was as eager and zealous as ever in the cause of geographical discovery. In July 1620 we find Sir Richard Hawkins going, in command of the *Vanguard*, as Vice-Admiral of a fleet of twenty ships, under Sir Robert Mansell as Admiral, for suppressing Algerine pirates; and in October a special commission was issued to Hawkins, to be Admiral in case of Mansell's death. Then comes a letter announcing the end. "Sir Robert Mansell and his crew are ill-paid and Sir Richard Hawkins, the Vice-Admiral, has died of vexation."

This is in a letter from the Lord Chamberlain to Sir Dudley Carlton dated April 17th, 1622. He was seized with a fit, it is said, when actually in the chamber of the Privy Council on business connected with his command. His will, dated on April 16th, 1622, was proved by his widow on June 13th of the same year. He is described as of Slapton in Devonshire, and owner of the manor of Pole, as well as of a house called Pryvitt, at Alverstoke in Hampshire. His widow followed him to the grave in 1629, and lies buried in the north aisle of Slapton Church. A slate slab, with an inscription round it, marks the spot, but one side and part of both ends are obliterated. There remains...

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Sir Richard Hawkins was actually passing his work through the press, at the time of his very sudden death; and it was published immediately afterwards with a dedication to Charles, Prince of Wales, by the author, and a short notice by another hand. The following is the entry in the Register of Stationers' Hall...

"1622, 24 Julii.

Master John Jaggard
entred for his copie under the handes of
Wilson and Master Gilwyn a book called
*The discipline of the sea historie, in the
observations which Sir Richard Hawkins
made in his South Sea voyage, anno
domini, 1593, vj.*"

The actual title page of the work, published by Jaggard in 1622, will be found at page 83 of the

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present volume. Purchas, in his *Pilgrims*, reprinted the *Observations of Sir Richard Hawkins* in a mutilated form—“once before published, now reviewed and corrected by a written copie, illustrated with notes, and in divers places abbreviated”. The reprint of the Hakluyt Society⁴⁰ is from the original edition of 1622. Admiral Burney devotes an interesting chapter to the voyage of Sir Richard Hawkins. A poetical relation of the voyage is preserved in the British Museum, composed by William Ridley in his nineteenth year.

Sir Richard intended to have given an account of his long imprisonment, and of Peru and Tierra Firme, Terceira, and Spain, in a second part, as he informs us at the end of his *Observations* (see p. 329). Death prevented the accomplishment of this intention, and the loss of the promised second part is a serious and irreparable loss to history. For we possess no account of Peru during that period, written by an observant foreigner.

40 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Hakluyt_Society
<https://www.hakluyt.com>

Another distinguished seaman of this family was **William**, brother of Sir John and uncle of Sir Richard Hawkins. He was not only an adventurous sea captain but also a large owner of ships, and in 1568 his Plymouth cruisers were the terror of the Spaniards. In 1582 he made the voyage to the West Indies, with his nephew Richard, which has already been referred to. He died on the 7th of October 1589, having had eleven children by two wives, and his brother Sir John put up a monument to his memory (now removed) in the church of St. Nicholas at Deptford, with the following inscription...

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Several of the sons of William Hawkins of Plymouth were sailors or merchants. But the most famous was he who bore the same name as his father. We first hear of **WILLIAM HAWKINS (junior)** as Lieutenant-General of Fenton's fleet in 1582. He had previously been in some voyage to Magellan's Straits, and also in the West Indies. Edward Fenton, a Nottinghamshire man, was appointed by Martin Frobisher as captain of the *Gabriel* in the second Arctic voyage of 1577, and he also accompanied Frobisher in the third voyage as Rear-Admiral in the *Judith*. Four years afterwards Fenton was selected, by the Earl of Leicester, to command an expedition nominally to discover the north-west passage. The Queen contributed two of her ships. One was the galleon *Leicester* of 400 tons with Fenton on board as general. The other was the *Bonaventure* of 300 tons, commanded by Luke Ward, as Vice-Admiral. There were also the *Francis* of 40 tons, under Captain John Drake, with William Markham as master; and the *Elizabeth* pinnace. The instructions were ambiguous and absurd. Fenton was to discover the north-west passage if it was to be found south of 40° N., but he was not to go north of that parallel, and he was to visit the Moluccas. But he was not to pass the Straits of Magellan. In short, he was to discover the north-west passage by going round the Cape of Good Hope to the East Indies, and enriching himself and his employers by trade and plunder.

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The journal of the voyage was kept by Mr. Maddox, the chaplain of the Leicester; and William Hawkins also kept a journal which is now in the British Museum (*MSS. Otho*, E viii), but much mutilated by fire. What can be deciphered will be found at pages 353 to

363 of the present volume. The expedition sailed in May 1582, and on July 20th the coast of Guinea was sighted. It appears to have been a most unhappy cruise, and the journal of Hawkins is full of complaints of the ill treatment he received from Captain Fenton. It is clear that Fenton wanted to abandon the voyage at a very early period, and that most of the officers protested against it. The *Francis* reached the river Plate, where she was wrecked, but the crew were saved and kept among the savages for fifteen months. The other ships entered the port of St. Vincent in Brazil, where an action was fought with a Spanish fleet by moonlight, and next morning, until both sides were weary. The English then made the best of their way home; and the *Leicester* arrived at Kinsale on June 14th, 1513. On reaching the Downs Fenton broke out in violent abuse of Hawkins, calling him a knave, a villain, and a boy; and the voyage ended in mutual reproaches. It was an utter failure. Fenton, however, does not appear to have lost any credit.

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We do not hear of William Hawkins again until 1607; but he appears to have been in the Levant, and to have learnt Turkish; for he could converse in that language. In 1607 he was captain of the *Hector* in the third voyage set forth by the East India Company. Captain Keelinge, in the *Dragon*, was general of the voyage. Purchas gives an abstract of Keelinge's Journal occupying eighteen pages, and another abstract of the Journal of Captain Hawkins of the same length. In my Introduction to the *Voyages of Sir James Lancaster*, have stated that the manuscript of the Journal of Hawkins was lost. It should be in the collection of East India Company's logs in the India Office. It has since been found among the manuscripts in the British Museum (*Egerton MS. 2100*); but much injured by damp. All that can be deciphered will be found at pages 364 to 388 of the present volume. This is followed by the interesting account of the "occurrences which happened in the time of his residence in India", and the "briefe discourse of the strength, wealth, and government, with some of the customs of the *Great Mogol*", reprinted from Purchas.

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The journey of William Hawkins to Agra, and his residence at the court of Jehanghir, may be looked

upon as the opening scene in the history of British India. The Emperor induced the English captain to marry the daughter of Mubarik Khan, a Christian Armenian; and when Hawkins was dismissed from Agra in November 1611, he took his native wife with him. They got safely on board Sir Henry Middleton's ship in the following January, and proceeded to Bantam, whence they sailed for England in the *Thomas*, arriving at Saldanha Bay on April 21st, 1613. The *Thomas* sailed from Saldanha Bay on May 21st, 1613, and here the letter (or report) of Hawkins to the company terminates abruptly. He died on the passage from the Cape, and was buried in Ireland.

Mrs. Hawkins, alone amongst strangers, was left in a very forlorn condition. But she had one diamond worth £2000, and smaller ones worth £4000, so that she had no difficulty in finding another husband. In 1614 she married Gabriel Towerson, who had been in the voyage of Captain Saris and brought home the *Hector*. In 1617 Captain and Mrs. Towerson went out to India again, and visited Agra; where the lady remained with her relations. Towerson went home, and in 1620 he was appointed Principal Factor at the Moluccas, where he was judicially murdered, after suffering inhuman treatment from the Dutch, on February 27th, 1623. He was the chief victim in the Massacre of Amboyna.

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